

TO STUDY THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. *The study's goal was to evaluate the similarity between the source language and its translations in light of the translators' chosen translation methods. This study concentrated on how amplification and transposition strategies appeared in imperative sentences, particularly commands. The qualitative method was used to carry out the study. Research methods used in this project included observation and library research. A descriptive qualitative analysis was performed on the data that had been gathered. We can talk about information concerning the transposition and translation of word categories in English in this article.*

Keywords: *transposition, translation, English, word classes, process.*

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВАЖНОСТЬ ТРАНСПОЗИЦИИ КАТЕГОРИЙ СЛОВ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. *Цель исследования состояла в том, чтобы оценить сходство между исходным языком и его переводами в свете выбранных переводчиками методов перевода. Это исследование было сосредоточено на том, как стратегии амплификации и транспозиции проявлялись в повелительных предложениях, особенно в командах. Для проведения исследования был использован качественный метод. Методы исследования, использованные в этом проекте, включали наблюдение и поиск в библиотеке. На собранных данных был проведен описательный качественный анализ. В этой статье мы можем поговорить об информации, касающейся транспонирования и перевода категорий слов в английском языке.*

Ключевые слова: *транспозиция, перевод, английский язык, классы слов, процесс.*

INTRODUCTION

Every human has a unique set of linguistic traits, hence translation was necessary in order to completely grasp one language in another. The translator must employ a technique when translating the documents in order to avoid the problematic translation. Humans employed language as a form of communication to express their thoughts, ideas, and feelings verbally or in writing. Every human has a unique set of linguistic traits, hence translation was necessary in order to completely grasp one language in another. Global communication has an essential role in translation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, the ability to convey messages from one language into another is known as translation. According to (Nida, 1975), translation is the creation of a translated version that is nearly equivalent and makes sense. According to recent reports, the translation industry is under pressure from automation, declining pricing, and worldwide competition (Vieira, 2020). Producing the closest natural counterpart of the source language's message in the target language, first in terms of meaning and then in terms of style, is what this activity entails. Bell (1991) claimed that translation was best understood as an endeavor to find equivalence.

Language and its components, including its levels of classification, rules, and phonology, are inextricably linked to translation (Catford, 1965). It was a difficult task to translate the communications from the source language into the target language. Every language had distinctive grammatical and cultural features. The translator must employ a technique when translating the documents in order to avoid the problematic translation caused by the various linguistic backgrounds. A technique is a specific approach of carrying out an action, particularly one for which you need to develop specialized knowledge.

The four main word classes in English are nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. These words are lexical in nature and give a phrase or sentence its primary meaning. Prepositions, pronouns, determiners, conjunctions, and interjections make up the other five word classes. These words are regarded as useful because they offer structural and relational details within a sentence or phrase.

RESULTS

The words we use to describe things like people, places, things, feelings, concepts, etc. are called nouns. Nouns are typically observable (touchable) objects like a table, a person, or a structure. We also have abstract nouns, which are things like love, honor, or enthusiasm that we may experience and describe but may not be able to see or touch. The names we give to distinct and official individuals, places, or objects, like England, Claire, or Hoover, are known as proper nouns.

Verbs are words that describe an action, circumstance, emotion, or mental state. This could involve a physical occurrence or action, or it might just be a mood.

Auxiliary verbs are not included in the list of the four major word classes, although lexical verbs are. Lexical verbs, such as "walk," "run," "felt," and "desire," are the main verbs in sentences that express action, an occurrence, a state of being, or all of these; in contrast, auxiliary verbs support the main verb.

Adjectives are words that are used to describe or modify nouns. Adjectives characterize a noun's feature, virtue, or state of being.

Words that function with verbs, adjectives, and other adverbs are called adverbs. They go on to describe in further detail how, when, where, and how frequently something is done.

Prepositions, pronouns, determiners, conjunctions, and interjections make up the final five word classes. These terms serve as an explanation of the grammatical and structural relationships between words and are regarded as functional words. Prepositions, for instance, can be used to describe how one thing is related to another.

Prepositions are used to show the relationship between words in terms of place, time, direction, and agency.

Pronouns take the place of a noun or a noun phrase in a sentence. They often refer to a noun that has already been mentioned and are commonly used to avoid repetition.

1. Chloe (noun) → she (pronoun)
2. Chloe's dog → her dog (possessive pronoun)

There are several different types of pronouns; let's look at some examples of each.

Determiners are used in conjunction with nouns to provide details like as the amount, location, or owner of the noun. It determines precisely what is being discussed. Determiners come in a variety of distinct forms, just like pronouns.

Conjunctions are the words in a sentence that link other words, phrases, and clauses together. The three primary categories of conjunctions are:

1. Coordinating conjunctions - these link independent clauses together.
2. Subordinating conjunctions - these link dependent clauses to independent clauses.
3. Correlative conjunctions - words that work in pairs to join two parts of a sentence of equal importance.

DISCUSSION

Exclamatory words used to express an emotion or a reaction are called interjections. They frequently contain an exclamation mark and stand off from the remainder of the text.

To better comprehend lexical word classes, think of them as the elements of sentences. The function word classes are the glue that holds the words together and gives the sentence structure if the lexical word classes are the building blocks themselves.

To transpose is to shift a category of grammar. Shift in translation was produced. Structure shift, class shift, and unit shift were the three components of the shift category identified by this study's data. This study focused on assessing English commands and their translation into Indonesian commands by employing two types of translation strategies that were found in the novel: amplification and transposition. The study's target did not involve any volunteers. Therefore, the methods of data collection used in this study were observation and library research.

CONCLUSIONS

It's crucial to learn how to teach English word categories in simple ways while studying them. The translation process also heavily relies on the transposition of word groups. I want to warn all teachers of young learners, especially those who work with primary school-aged children, that they shouldn't assume that their students will speak English naturally. They may only be able to interact and communicate in a very restricted number of ways, even if they are proficient in some very fundamental English forms and functions. So have that in mind. Be patient if they are having trouble speaking. You'll be surprised at how far they can go if you give them time to do their task. The most crucial thing is to possess is to have a deep knowledge of word classes in learning the English language.

REFERENCES

1. Komilova, N. (2022). GENDERED LEXICON OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 192-194.
2. Sotvoldiyevna, U. D. (2022). Political Euphemisms in English and Uzbek Languages (A Comparative Analysis). *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 9, 92-96.
3. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
4. Satvoldievna, U. D. (2021). Axiological Characteristics Of English, Uzbek And Russian Phraseological Units. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 40-45.

5. Mirzayeva, D. (2019). PROVERB AS A KIND OF PAREMIOLOGICAL FUND AND AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC AND METHODOLOGICAL RESEARCH. *Мировая наука*, (11), 33-36.
6. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 392-399.
7. Mirzaeva, D. (2021). THE ROLE OF PAREMIA IN THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL CULTURAL HERITAGE. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(3).
8. Soxibovna, M. G. (2022, August). THE ROLE OF LINVOCULTUREME IN THE STUDY OF NATIONAL AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF SPEECH UNITS. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 48-52).